

A STUDY ON TEACHERS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL SYSTEM: A CASE STUDY OF GARISSA TOWNSHIP SUB-COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract:

Performance appraisal system is lately adopted by most companies and organizations to evaluate individual employee in order to get a clear picture of the specific employee. As much as the organizations have taken up the initiative of developing the tool, questions like is it useful, has it impacted on the productivity of these employees and how effective is it must be answered and well ventilated. The study dwelled and sought to answer the above questions on Teachers Service Commission of Kenya's performance appraisal system through the teachers it has employed in the public schools in Garissa township sub-county. It was, through this research, found out that the general perception level among teachers towards the tool is positive. Teachers have seen it to be a good idea. It was also found that majority of the respondents were satisfied with the effectiveness of the system. The tool is quite effective in achieving the objective it was developed for. However, respondents were for the opinion that it has no impact on their work productivity. Work productivity depends on other factors including in-service training, motivation, clear mechanisms of promotion including academic qualification etc. it was also found out that the tool is useful but must be updated periodically to cater for various needs. In conclusion, the performance appraisal tool developed by Teachers Service Commission (TSC) called Teachers performance Appraisal and Development (TPAD) got approval from majority of the respondents in terms of its general perception, effectiveness and its usefulness to the teaching fraternity. However to get maximum production from the employees, the employer must also enhance all the factors mentioned by the teachers including clear criteria for promotion in order to achieve its set objectives.

Keywords: performance appraisal, productivity, perception, satisfaction

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1. Introduction

Performance appraisal is an important tool in evaluating employee's performance achievements. Employers engage in annual, termly or quarterly performance appraisals through a set performance management systems (PMS) that will give picture on individual, unit or departments achievements in order to identify if set goals were achieved or not then plan for best remedies. It is important to note that effective performance appraisal system rest on its acceptability among the employees so that it can efficiently function. The various techniques that can be used include the following: essay appraisal, forced ranking, person to person ranking, critical incidents, graphic review scale, and management by objectives and 360 degree feedback.

Kenya's Teachers Service commission introduced the performance appraisal system in 2015. It is called Teachers performance Appraisal and Development (TPAD) generally developed for classroom teachers and performance contracting for head teachers and principals. It is to be filled through online provided by Teachers Service Commission (TSC) at the end of each term. Each teacher employed by the commission has to appraise himself first before he is appraised by his/her senior. They have to agree on the evaluation before submitting. In case they don't agree the ratings, then an arbitrator will be involved to listen to the dissenting cases.

Though it has generated conflicts between the employer and teachers unions, the tool was successfully rolled out in all public schools. This study therefore depicts to find out if the performance appraisal system achieved its set objectives through looking at the perception of teachers towards the tool, to identify the usefulness of the tool, the impact of the system on individual teachers' productivity and the effectiveness of the performance appraisal used. The study focused on public school teachers both in primary and post primary in Garissa Township of Garissa County, Kenya. The county is situated in the northern part of Kenya bordering Wajir, Isiolo and Tana River counties. The county also borders Somalia. 100 teachers and tutors were engaged in this exercise. The teachers were selected randomly from various schools. Gender, age and years of service of respondents were carefully considered to get the accurate results and achieve the objectives set.

2. Literature Review

According to Brumbrach (1998, cited in Armstrong, 2000) performances are actions followed by consequences. He says though these consequences are desired but still a different outcome cannot be ruled out. To get this, instruments and tools have to be used. Behaviors towards the performance of these tools are also important and must be considered. Because of this performance can be attributed to actions and behaviors taken during process in anticipation of attaining goals and other desired objectives.

The need for top management to deal and handle employees' opinions in developing the tool in order to accomplish desired performance is considered crucial. Evaluation has to be developed in order to establish the rate and standards at which the

goals have been achieved. It concludes that performance should be based on decision and action taken with existing findings and results. Actions taken should be informed by these findings. Loopholes should be sealed at the earliest opportunity.

According to Fisher (1995:11), "*Performance appraisal is a process of management which deals with improving the organizations performance through individuals enhanced performance*" he depicts that individual's specific performance affects the organization directly. So he recommends that performance appraisal should be enhanced effectively to increase productivity. Systematic evaluation with well thought of should be worked out for the employees. (Parill, 1999) forwards that performance appraisal should form a significant component of organizations in order to basically better performance. He says that organizations should develop their workers competencies and capabilities and then develop a relevant performance appraisal. Rewards should be distributed as per the performances of the evaluated employees.

According to Redman (2001), performance appraisal has become an important and widespread tool to assess members of staff as per the set objectives of the concerned organization. He says that the tool has also become an important factor to easily identify hardworking and dedicated employees. Because of this important factor, he says, performance appraisal has become widely used performance management tool.

According to Dunker (1984), he opined that both private and public have adopted performance appraisal systems. He found out that this is basically because developing a working performance appraisal systems is begged on workers' productivity. Lack of it will deem difficult to measure and evaluate who has performed and who has not performed. Some workers may take advantage of the situation. This may lead to failure of the organization. According to Noel et al (1996), the performance appraisal system is duty to both the organization and the employees because the system measures output and can easily be aligned to the objectives set for the organization. He says many organizations have adopted annual performance review in measuring performance of their staff. He depicted that the system if well planned and developed gives an overboard competitive advantage over competitors.

Grote (2002) described performance appraisal to be a management that is considered formal across all organizations that engage in evaluating the quality of performance by employees. He says that the system helps identify and develops performance of the targeted employees. It helps in understanding who did what and how. It is geared towards proper communication between the organization and the workers specifically directed towards their individual performance. It is a source of data documentation, planning and making informed decisions.

2. Methodology

2.1 Sampling

This is an important dimension of data gathering. It is generally concerned with the selection of specific observation with the objective of deducing and inducing conclusion. In this particular study, 100 teachers and tutors were selected to represent

the population. The selection was done carefully to capture the demography the teaching fraternity. .

2.2 Sources of Data Collection

- Primary sources: this was done through structured questionnaire to the sample selected in line with the set objectives.
- Secondary sources: relevant information from past records, newspapers, journals, articles and booklets were collected and reviewed.

2.3 Tools and Techniques for Data Collection

The data was collected through observation, well planned interviews and administering the structured questionnaire to the selected sample population. Periodicals, reports, articles and relevant books were also reviewed.

2.4 Plan of Analysis

The data obtained was tabulated against the respondents. The corresponding percentages were also given. It was then captured on bar and pie charts to analyze and give accurate interpretation. Any wrong inferences, inaccurate, wrong and dishonest responses were eliminated.

2.5 Objectives of the study

The study is determined to achieve the following objectives;

- A. To establish the teachers' perception on the performance appraisal system.
- B. To determine the effectiveness of the performance appraisal used
- C. To analyze the impact of the system on teachers' productivity.
- D. To understand the overall usefulness of the appraisal system used on teachers.

3. Findings and Discussion

3.1 Perception level

What is your perception level on the performance appraisal system?

Table 1: Perception level

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Very Good	27	27.0
Good	32	32.0
Average	26	26.0
Poor	10	10.0
Very Poor	5	5.0
Total	100	100.0

3.1.1 Analysis

When teachers were asked about how they perceive the performance appraisal system in place, more than half of the respondents have said that it's good. Only 15% have rated it to be poor and very poor. 26% of the respondents have rated it to be average.

Chart 1: Perception level

3.1.2 Interpretation

According to the responses given, the perception level of the teachers towards the performance appraisal system is positive. More than 85% of the respondents have no issues with the performance appraisal system in place.

3.2 Satisfaction level

What is your satisfaction level of the effectiveness of the appraisal system?

Table 2: Satisfaction level

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Satisfied	19	19.0
Satisfied	48	48.0
Average	21	21.0
Dissatisfied	10	10.0
Strongly Dissatisfied	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

3.2.1 Analysis

When teachers were asked about their satisfaction level towards the effectiveness of the appraisal system, close to 70% were either satisfied or strongly satisfied. 12% were dissatisfied or strongly dissatisfied as shown in the table above. A fifth of all the respondents have rated it to be average.

Chart 2: Satisfaction Level

3.2.2 Interpretation

As per the responses received and shown on the graph above, majority of the teachers are satisfied with its effectiveness. If joined with those who rated the system as average, then close to 90% of all the respondents have positively rated the system. This means the performance appraisal system is effective and hence can achieve its objective

3.3 Impact on productivity

How do you rate the performance appraisal system's impact on productivity?

Table 3: Impact on productivity

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Very High	8	8.0
High	22	22.0
Average	28	28.0
Low	30	30.0
Very Low	12	12.0
Total	100	100.0

3.3.1 Analysis

When teachers were asked about as the performance appraisal system impacted on their productivity, only 30% rated it as high or very high impact. 28% of the respondents gave it average ratings, while 42% said it has a low or very low impact.

Chart 3: Impact on Productivity

3.3.2 Interpretation

As per the responses given by the teachers, the performance appraisal system has had a low impact on their productivity. Work productivity does not necessarily depend on the performance appraisal system but rather on other factors including dedication, experience, motivation, training etc. so as much as the tool is used for evaluation, all other factors should be enhanced.

3.4 Usefulness

Table 4: The usefulness of the appraisal system

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	46	46.0
No	39	39.0
Don't know	15	15.0
Total	100	100.0

3.4.1 Analysis

When teachers were asked about how useful the tool is to the teaching fraternity, 46% said it is useful while a close percentage of 39 downplayed its usefulness. 15% of the respondents said they don't know if it is useful or not.

Chart 4: Usefulness of the appraisal system

3.4.2 Interpretation

Given that, those who said it is useful and those who responded "it is not useful" are close at 46% and 39%, teachers are almost divided on the tool. Those who said "it is useful", cited the way it has improved teachers absenteeism, class attendance and development of professional records, while those who responded to the negative, have based their argument that it can easily be manipulated through collusion between the appraisee and the appraiser, it has no impact on the productivity of the teachers and lack of proper follow up on the results of the appraisal.

4. Conclusion

Performance appraisal system needs planning, development, implementation and management so that set standards can be maintained. The tool should be tailor made for the employees targeted or else it will fail. Stakeholder involvement is also very important at the planning and development stage. Reviewing and updating of the tool should also be considered. This can be done to integrate any pertinent and emerging issues as the world has become so dynamic.

The performance appraisal system developed by TSC is periodically updated to capture any new development in the sector. It has covered all the teachers in public primary and secondary schools. Tertiary institutions including Teacher Training Colleges (TTCs) will be brought on board on 1st of April 2018 as their TPAD is different from the rest of teachers. With regular development, commitment from stakeholders including field officers, well use of the results from the TPAD for promotion and career growth and detecting collusion among the actors, the purpose of the system will be achieved. Let me sincerely thank all those who participated in this noble exercise including teachers, head teachers, principals and officers from both TSC and ministry of education.

5.1 Recommendation

Teachers service commission has tried its best make sure all teachers are appraised. This is important as it will help evaluate teachers' performance. However, the following recommendations should be considered for proper implementation;

1. Develop clear mechanisms to reduce/stop collusion between the appraise and appraiser
2. Results and the outcome of the appraisals should be used for career growth and development so that teachers can understand the importance of the appraisals.
3. Field officers including county directors should be more committed to the tool implementation
4. There should be proper documentation of the appraisals especially in hard copies.

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